

Pre-electoral coalitions in Brazil: a quick survey

The literature devoted to the study of electoral coalitions can be subdivided into two major work fronts. In general terms, these two fronts analyzed the adoption of pre-electoral alliances in elections under two historical contexts: the political system of the fourth republic, in the so-called populist republic (1946-1964), and the contemporary republican period, then dedicated to the configurations assumed by the political system after the opening of 1980 (Dantas, 2007; Schmitt, 1999, Krause and Schmitt, 2005; Simas, 1999, Sousa, 2006). In addition to these two historical frameworks, these two fronts converged in investigating the effects of coalitions, almost always, on General Elections (Krause and Schmitt, 2005; Dantas, 2007).

The analytical concerns of the first studies dialogues with the main archetypes of modern parties and party systems (Duverger, 1970; Panebianco, 2005) and developed interpretations of various shades. On the rationality, functionality, volume, typification, selection of partners and ideological consistency of the exclusively electoral associations celebrated by the parties, on their electoral consequences for the majority system and on proportional ones, on the diffusion of political parties and the configuration of the party system between States (Campello de Souza, 1990; Lavareda, 1999; Lima Júnior 1983, 1993; Soares 1964). In summary, these works carry a good part of the main hypotheses that guide the theoretical constructions on this front of the field. In general terms, a series of studies have shown that the theory of economy of effort (Downs, 1999) and electoral rationality (Figueiredo, 2004) are factors that have prevailed, with explanatory capacity in electorally competitive scenarios, where ideology has taken over, the with each new election, a decreasing weight as a resistance factor for the formation of alliances (Santos, 1987), as well as other more classic social and economic structural constraints (Soares 1964).

Studies dedicated to analyzing inter-party associations in a municipal context identify several main trends: the diffusion of party legends (Peixoto, 2010; Speck and Campos, 2014), an increase in the effective number of electoral parties and the fragmentation of municipal councils (Ferreira, Batista, Stabile, 2008; Guarnieri, 2015; Krause and Barbosa, 2020; Krause, Paiva, Ribeiro and Melo, 2013; Peixoto and Goulart, 2014), in the increase in the diversification of preferred partners among almost all the most relevant parties (largest, and in the largest municipalities) with remarkable freedom of association in smaller municipalities, not correlated with socioeconomic factors (Peixoto, 2007, 2010), reduction of ideological congruence or consistency (Carreirão, 2006; Miguel and Machado, 2007) promoted by factors such as the nationalization of parties (Peixoto, 2010; Miguel and Machado, 2010; Speck and Campos, 2014), or the presidentialization of municipal electoral disputes (Borges, 2015, 2018, 2019; Sandes-Freitas, 2013, 2015; Sandes-Freitas and Bizzarro

Neto, 2018), and the broad autonomy of subnational sections of parties politicians (Dantas and Praça, 2004, 2010; Ribeiro, 2004, 2006, 2010). Summing up: “the main Brazilian parties have learned to play the game of coalitions” (Krause, Paiva, Ribeiro e Melo, 2013; Ribeiro, 2010), and this game tends to follow, preponderantly, logics inherent to the electoral system, its main incentives and their most pronounced barriers. Despite changes in electoral rules being relatively recent, several works have already mobilized efforts and collected their findings (Cervi and Neves, 2019; Fisch and Mesquita, 2022; Kerbauy, Peixoto, Melo, Marques, 2020; Krause, Mancuso and Schaefer, 2020; Matheus, 2021; Santos and Sandes-Freitas, 2020; Speck, 2016, 2022; Nicolau, 2023; Peixoto, Marques and Ribeiro, 2022). However, endeavors that prioritize and perform causal effects models are still rare. Works that take social, demographic, economic, and political-institutional variables to control, accommodate, and identify the essential causal chains that rule the relationship between all of them are even rarer.

In general, the collection of studies, hypotheses and findings, exclusively dedicated to municipalities (Lavareda and Telles, 2015; 2016; 2022) and electoral coalitions in Municipal Elections (Krause and Schmitt, 2005; Krause, Dantas and Miguel, 2010; Krause, Machado and Miguel, 2017) has increased substantially in the last 15 years. However, elections to city councils, which are actual entry points for most politicians (Peixoto, Goulart, 2014; Dantas, Silva, 2020), precisely because they are the least expensive campaigns and the most tangible, given their circumscription, have yet to be. Although the first works dedicated to subnational electoral and party systems emerged and spread with greater consistency after the 2000s, this niche of investigation still needs to be explored compared to other federal scopes. However, disseminating data and indicators that exist today makes these (municipal) scenarios proper laboratories for tests and theoretical investigations based on evidence. Precisely, aiming to deepen previous investigations (Goulart, 2020, 2022), this proposal intends to explore these fronts mainly by carrying out causal studies dedicated to proportional electoral analyzes of more than five thousand municipalities, exploring recent constructions in the literature (Calvo, Guarnieri and Limongi, 2015).

Research problem statement, propositional main answer and starting hypotheses

The main question of this research proposal has two fronts. One will address "What are the main effects of electoral coalitions on candidate lists (nominates) in proportional electoral disputes, specifically?" The second will try to identify "What did the most recent changes to this institutional variable (permission for inter-party association) cause in the configuration of these Brazilian political subsystems, in general?" To minimally address this double-edged questioning, my central concern in this proposal is to build an investigative workflow that handles i. identify, ii. measure, and iii. explain the main factors that led the parties to coordinate the performances of their candidates' perfor-

mances systematically in the municipal elections between 2012 and 2020 and according to the dispositions of the votes between the individual candidates presented in Figure 01 below.

Figure 01. The votes' concentration of party lists positions, 2012 – 2020.¹

Methodological Note: $N_{s01}, N_{s02} \dots N_{s0L}$ are groups formed according to the voting positions of candidates in the party lists. N_{s01} is the party candidate group with the highest number of votes between municipalities, the first placed among all party labels in all proportional municipal elections of the year for all cities in Brazil. N_{s02} is the next group, with the second-highest votes. The construction of groups of voting positions continues until the last-voted candidates conform to the N_{s0L} group or groups of the last-highest votes. The first dashed line is the Candidate Performance Clause (0.10). The second dashed line demarcates half of the roll-call votes (0.50).

Descriptive Note: The statistics of the proportions of votes obtained by the most voted candidates of each party list (N_{s01}) take more than half of the votes in 2012 and 2016. In 2020, this high concentration of votes in the first candidates was significantly reduced, reducing the inequality of intra-party ballots within the same list.

From the outset, this indicates the incidence of two phenomena: concentration of votes in very few names on the lists and eventual rational use of nominees and candidates that are not very viable. There is an accentuated directing of votes to the first place, which results in a system of high concentration capacity. On the other hand, it indicates that the strategic entry of nominee partners occurred, at least to some extent, prioritizing names with low electoral viability. The system reaches its support capacity after one or two candidacies (N_{s01}, N_{s02}), leaving the luck to the other nominees. As everything indicates, the chances are meager for candidates who assume positions that are in the third position (N_{s03}). These initial data expand (for the municipal area) and corroborate relevant findings about the causal mechanisms that govern the entry logic of applications, as reported in recent literature (Calvo, Guarneri, and Limongi, 2015). Between 2012 and 2020, party labels promoted several “Pen’s parades” for municipal elections in Brazil. Only in the last elections, and primarily due to legal changes, did the parties coordinate their nominations in the sense of providing less inequality of votes between the names on the list and meeting the Performance Clause of the Candidates (10% of the Electoral Quotient).

In a municipal context, less evident and professionalized, concerning the State and Federal fields, my initial interpretative proposition is that electoral coalitions functioned as formal means of coordinating teams of candidates that are mixed teams of viable and strategically unfeasible candidates (Wylie, Santos, Marcelino, 2019), with official electoral officers "contracted" under the nomi-

¹ For a preview of the preliminary data, please access the following: GOULART, Nelson Luis Motta; Tisse da Silva, Gabriel. elebra-data: competição eleitoral intrapartidária (0.2.0), Banco de dados, 2020 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4299756>). GOULART, Nelson Luis Motta. elebra-data: competição eleitoral interpartidária (0.2.0), Banco de dados, 2020 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4299220>).

nates. This meant that, throughout past elections, the electoral system that prioritized the figure of candidates (Ames, 1995a, 1995b), in addition to doing so, promoted the concentration and monopoly of parties in the use of few champions (Samuels, 1997), few candidates with good chances (Avelino, 1994). Consequently, the open predisposition in the system meant that intra-party competition (as shown in Figure 01), the distribution of economic resources in campaigns (Avelino and Fisch, 2018), and the distribution of votes between the positions of the party nominees converged, after a cut-off position, to an exponential format of significantly decreasing odds. Even if eventually, this breaks the possibility of any rational arithmetic of the candidate that calculates his vote predictions, leaving virtually luck to the candidates who were beyond the thirds positions. Has that changed with the latest renovations?

Study Design: Materials, Methods, and Techniques

In summary, the main objective of this study is to explore a parsimonious collection of variables in a general equation way of integrating them in the three phases of investigation². In the first phase, I adopt a naive approach, which involves applying a series of exploratory analyses using a collection of three models: pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, weighted OLS regression, and a model based on the means of the variables for the entire period (between OLS) to explore the following question: **what are the primary correlates of a pre-electoral coalition strategy adoption?** First, I stack the data for the first case and assume all the best model fitting conditions. I check for heteroscedasticity issues in the second case and modify the variance-covariance matrix. In the third and final case, I adopt a strategy to exclude omitted effects.

In this second phase, I will focus on the legal and social correlates of the effective number of political parties to answer the research question: **do pre-electoral coalitions promote the local political party's system growth?** Thus, I advance and analyze the established hypotheses with an approach that I consider appropriate for the research question and the structure of many cases (i) and few time units (t) (short dynamic panel data models). The exploratory path adopted aims to use three estimation techniques for dynamic panel models. Specifically, I employ the estimation of first-difference two-stage least squares (TSLS) as proposed by Anderson and Hsiao (1981, 1982); the analysis of the generalized method of moments (GMM) based on first differences (Difference GMM Estimators), following Arellano and Bond (1991); and the estimation of a System GMM model proposed by Blundell and Bond (1998). By doing so, I address the issues of heteroscedasticity, serial correlation of the data, and endogeneity.

² For the list of variables, the most generic form of the regression equation, and to check the basic analytical stance on the adopted variables and the initial modeling, please access the following:

In the third and final stage of the investigation, I will analyze the causal impact of legal interventions on the realization of electoral coalitions and the political parties' adoption of the coalitionist strategy: **have electoral law reforms made political parties promote new resources and vote distributions between their nominees in party lists?** To this end, I will work with some previously mentioned techniques, however, under a new mode of data accommodation: before, I was comparing and using data from balanced municipal panels (*i*) over the years (*t*) in the elections comprised between 1996 and 2020; in the current phase, I will explore the potential of data from unbalanced panels of parties (*i*) in the municipal elections of 2012, 2016 and 2020. My main objective in this phase will be to measure electoral coordination regimes at the level of party enterprises, in the management of the most relevant candidates of each nominate and their impacts on the concentration of economic resources, on the concentration of the number of votes, and on the probability of obtaining seats.

Schedule

All stages and activities presented will follow the elaborated schedule, which contains quarterly and monthly records (between October 2023 (**O**) and August 2024 (**A**)) and may change according to supervisor's directions and contractor's demand.

Pré-electoral coalitions and party lists coordination: what can we learn from more than 25 years of associations between political parties in Brazilian proportional municipal elections?	QUARTERS											
	1			2			3			4		
	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	J	A
Continuous Research Flow	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			
Narrative review	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			
Systematic review				•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
First Phase: theoretical and operational integration	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			
Revision and update of relevant data	•	•	•	•	•	•						
Elaboration and assessment of adequacy of variables				•	•	•	•					
Formalization of hypotheses				•	•	•	•					
Second Phase: academic articulation and deepening				•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Disclosure of preliminary results and dissemination of data				•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Submission of <i>working papers</i>			•	•			•	•	•			
Phase Three: consolidation of search results				•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Disclosure of preliminary results and dissemination of data				•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Submission of <i>research articles</i>			•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•
Final Work Plan Report										•	•	•